

Automatic assessment of Footpad Dermatitis (FPD)

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Introduction

Footpad dermatitis (FPD) is a contact dermatitis that can lead to ulcerative lesions on the plantar surface of footpads in poultry. It is considered a reliable indicator of poultry welfare on farm, since footpad health correlates directly to litter quality, particularly wetness.

FPD monitoring is a common practice across the EU and different scoring scales have been defined that classify the extent and severity of FPD.

The scoring protocols most widely used in the EU are based on a 3-point scale system adapted from the Swedish scoring system (Berg, 1998), although at present, no common standardised FPD scoring protocol has been adopted in the EU.

Monitoring at the processing plant is generally performed manually, either on a random sample of feet severed from the carcasses or assessed on the slaughter line although the high line speed often makes it difficult. In general, samples consist in 100-200 feet per batch, since performing the scoring of all the feet manually would be too time consuming. Furthermore, manual scoring can result in grading inconsistencies because of human interpretation and therefore requires frequent calibration.

These issues can be addressed using automated monitoring systems based on image analysis, currently available on the market and installed in many EU poultry slaughter plants. Image analysis seems to be a promising approach to automatically evaluate FPD at the slaughterhouse, and the use of this technology is encouraged by product quality certification bodies in some EU member states.

Footpad Inspection Systems

The automated camera systems are installed as a fixed part of the slaughter line, positioned at the end of the line. At this stage, feet are more or less free of dirt, due to the preceding slaughter process (e.g., after scalding, plucking, and evisceration). After hocks are separated from the birds, they remain in the shackle and are transported to a hock positioning wheel, that ensures hocks are positioned correctly for an optimal image to be taken by the camera, aided by a bright LED light for optimal resolution and a blue back plate for optimal contrast.

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Camera image collection phase

For a proper image, the feet must be positioned appropriately on the shackle. Feet that are twisted/turned in the shackles, cannot be measured and are considered non-assessed in the software.

Using camera-based visual analysis, the system determines the size of black discoloration on the footpad and classifies the defects. The feet are scored according to the chosen classification scheme (3- or 5-point scale).

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Image of foot pad dermatitis assessed by the software

Both feet from a bird are assessed, some systems for the detection of footpad dermatitis use only the value from the most damaged foot while others use the mean value between the left and right foot.

The systems can evaluate up to 5 pairs of feet per second (up to 18.000 / hour). To assess FPD from the images correctly, it is necessary to regularly carry out the calibration practice, which is specific to each system.

For documentation purposes, records containing the detailed evaluation data as well as captured images are stored in a database (both empty and filled shackles). This includes the time of image acquisition, the determined quality level, the size of the discolouration, the associated flock number as well as the associated slaughter line. The data allow an individual evaluation of each flock.

Benefits and limitations of automatic FPD evaluation

The automated systems are designed to evaluate each individual in a flock without slowing down the slaughter process. This provides a more reliable picture of the incidence of footpad dermatitis in a flock compared to manual measurement which is based on a sample of the flock and can therefore have a significant effect on the final FPD score of the flock since the extent to which FPD can occur is not always evenly distributed in a flock.

Replacing human experts with an automated system will significantly increase the number of birds that can be assessed without an associated increase in labour costs and could lead to improvements in the standardisation of the evaluation process.

The data in the diagnostic database can be made available to research establishments for research projects and scientific evaluations in the field of animal welfare/animal health and to competent authorities to improve animal welfare monitoring and eventually set threshold values for FPD. However, automated FPD assessment systems require frequent and appropriate calibration to ensure reliable results. Furthermore, automatic assessment systems are based on image analysis, which is limited to considering only the size of the lesion and unlike human evaluation they cannot assess its actual depth. Depth is a very important factor as it provides information on the potential damage to the underlying tissues and hence the level of pain involved.

Finally, to be used by official inspectors in the application of animal welfare controls, clear validation procedures have not yet been specifically defined.

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